

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/raymond
hash://md5/6a819a23469766e71c64f253321548ae

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<https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/raymond/issues>

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/raymond, has fingerprint hash://md5/6a819a23469766e71c64f253321548ae, is 779KiB in size and contains 26,462 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 342 primary taxa (e.g., *Arctocephalus gazella*) and 915 associated taxa (e.g., Fish). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Raymond, B., Marshall, M., Nevitt, G., Gillies, C., van den Hoff, J., Stark, J.S., Losekoot, M., Woehler, E.J., and Constable, A.J. (2011) A Southern Ocean dietary database. *Ecology* 92(5):1188. Available from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1890/10-1907.1> . Data set supplied by Ben Raymond. <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/raymond/archive/a8bcc40af606e5677da715a2026-01-24T05:49:40.734Z> hash://md5/6a819a23469766e71c64f253321548ae

For additional metadata related to this dataset, please visit <https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/raymond> and inspect associated metadata files including, but not limited to, *README.md*, *eml.xml*, and/or *globi.json*.

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.1
nomer	0.5.17
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 779KiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/raymond

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/raymond\
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/raymond\
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/raymond\
| nomer append col\
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/raymond`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/raymond`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/raymond`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/raymond`)

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

filename	description
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomen Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format

filename	description
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/raymond`, has fingerprint hash://md5/6a819a23469766e71c64f253321548ae, is 779KiB in size and contains 26,462 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 342 primary taxa (e.g., *Arctocephalus gazella*) and 915 associated taxa (e.g., Fish).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 3: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Eukrohnia hamata	eats	Metridia gerlachei	Oresland, V. (1995) Winter population structure and feeding of the chaetognath Eukrohnia hamata and the copolopod Euchaeta antarctica in Gerlache Strait, Antarctic Peninsula. Marine Ecology Progress Series 119:77-86
Eukrohnia hamata	eats	Oncaea sp.	Oresland, V. (1995) Winter population structure and feeding of the chaetognath Eukrohnia hamata and the copolopod Euchaeta antarctica in Gerlache Strait, Antarctic Peninsula. Marine Ecology Progress Series 119:77-86

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Eukrohnia hamata	eats	Microcalanus pygmaeus	Oresland, V. (1995) Winter population structure and feeding of the chaetognath Eukrohnia hamata and the copepod Euchaeta antarctica in Gerlache Strait, Antarctic Peninsula. Marine Ecology Progress Series 119:77-86
Eukrohnia hamata	eats	Oithona sp.	Oresland, V. (1995) Winter population structure and feeding of the chaetognath Eukrohnia hamata and the copepod Euchaeta antarctica in Gerlache Strait, Antarctic Peninsula. Marine Ecology Progress Series 119:77-86

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eats	26462

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Arctocephalus gazella	1364
Trematomus bernacchii	1322
Notothenia neglecta	1171
Leptonychotes weddellii	971
Pygoscelis papua	818
Champscephalus gunnari	514
Dissostichus eleginoides	493
Halobaena caerulea	487
Paralabidocera antarctica	448
Diomedea exulans	433
Trematomus hansonii	412
Trematomus newnesi	410
Thalassarche chrysostoma	403
Procellaria aequinoctialis	401
Eudyptes chrysolophus	388
Catharacta maccormicki	375
Paraeuchaeta antarctica	346
Thalassarche melanophris	309
Phalacrocorax atriceps bransfieldensis	290

Table 6: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Fish	1729
Gammaridea	877
Crustacea	808
Euphausia superba	786
Unidentified	537
Polychaeta	519
Copepoda	511
Gastropoda	457
Cephalopoda	413
Amphipoda	403
Residue	383
Isopoda	350
Teuthida	330
Themisto gaudichaudii	281
Oithona sp.	257

targetTaxonName	count
Oncaea sp.	235
Metridia gerlachei	233
Plant material	229
Calanoides acutus	226

Table 7: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
Trematomus bernacchii	eats	Gammaridea	352
Notothenia neglecta	eats	Gammaridea	338
Trematomus bernacchii	eats	Polychaeta	220
Pygoscelis papua	eats	Fish	178
Notothenia neglecta	eats	Plant material	164
Pygoscelis papua	eats	Euphausia superba	151
Notothenia neglecta	eats	Gastropoda	149
Trematomus bernacchii	eats	Residue	146
Arctocephalus gazella	eats	Fish	136
Pygoscelis papua	eats	Unidentified	133
Notothenia neglecta	eats	Isopoda	124
Trematomus bernacchii	eats	Isopoda	100
Notothenia neglecta	eats	Fish	100
Trematomus bernacchii	eats	Fish	94
Trematomus newnesi	eats	Residue	84
Trematomus hansonii	eats	Fish	83
Trematomus newnesi	eats	Copepoda	82
Notothenia neglecta	eats	Polychaeta	79
Notothenia neglecta	eats	Residue	75

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life [download svg](#)

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at `indexed-interactions.gpkg` for point data and `indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg` for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 8: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abyssorchomene plebs	SYNONYM_OF	col	Pseudorchomene plebs

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abyssorchomene rossi	SYNONYM_OF	col	Pseudorchomene rossi
Abyssorchomene	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Abyssorchomene
Acanthephyra pelagica	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Acanthephyra pelagica

Table 9: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	96
col	class	26
col	family	86
col	genus	204
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraorder	3
col	kingdom	4
col	order	27
col	phylum	16
col	species	582
col	subclass	3
col	subfamily	1
col	subgenus	5
col	suborder	4
col	subphylum	2
col	subspecies	10
col	superfamily	4
col	superorder	3
col	tribe	1
discoverlife	NA	1062
gbif	NA	64
gbif	class	26
gbif	family	90
gbif	form	1
gbif	genus	240
gbif	kingdom	4
gbif	order	28
gbif	phylum	17
gbif	species	602
gbif	subspecies	9

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	NA	195
itis	class	26
itis	family	86
itis	genus	206
itis	infraorder	1
itis	kingdom	4
itis	order	27
itis	phylum	15
itis	species	473
itis	subclass	10
itis	subfamily	3
itis	suborder	5
itis	subphylum	3
itis	subspecies	7
itis	superclass	1
itis	superfamily	2
itis	superorder	1
mdd	NA	1061
ncbi	NA	206
ncbi	clade	3
ncbi	class	27
ncbi	family	87
ncbi	genus	208
ncbi	infraorder	3
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	order	29
ncbi	phylum	16
ncbi	species	463
ncbi	subclass	5
ncbi	suborder	6
ncbi	subphylum	2
ncbi	subspecies	1
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superfamily	3
ncbi	superkingdom	2
ncbi	superorder	3
pdb	NA	745
pdb	class	27
pdb	family	62
pdb	genus	67
pdb	informal	1
pdb	infraorder	2
pdb	kingdom	3
pdb	order	29

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	phylum	16
pbdb	species	94
pbdb	subclass	6
pbdb	subkingdom	1
pbdb	suborder	5
pbdb	subphylum	1
pbdb	subspecies	1
pbdb	superclass	1
pbdb	superfamily	1
pbdb	superorder	1
pbdb	superphylum	1
pbdb	tribe	1
pbdb	unranked clade	13
tpt	NA	985
tpt	family	5
tpt	genus	4
tpt	order	1
tpt	species	66
wfo	NA	1055
wfo	genus	5
wfo	phylum	1
worms	NA	47
worms	class	29
worms	family	85
worms	forma	1
worms	genus	217
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraclass	1
worms	infraorder	3
worms	kingdom	4
worms	order	31
worms	phylum	18
worms	species	599
worms	subclass	4
worms	subfamily	2
worms	suborder	6
worms	subphylum	3
worms	subspecies	6
worms	superfamily	3
worms	superorder	3
worms	tribe	1
worms	variety	1

Table 10: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	SYNONYM_OF	109
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	984
col	NONE	102
discoverlife	NONE	1094
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	138
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1089
gbif	NONE	74
itis	NONE	202
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	861
itis	SYNONYM_OF	43
mdd	NONE	1060
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	23
mdd	SYNONYM_OF	1
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	46
ncbi	SAME_AS	835
ncbi	NONE	223
pbdb	NONE	756
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	342
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	57
tpt	NONE	1005
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	77
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	2
wfo	NONE	1078
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	3
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4
worms	SYNONYM_OF	99
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	972
worms	NONE	53

Table 11: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 12: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-28T17:54:29Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@1cbb87f3"; line: 1, column: 4]

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-01-28T17:54:29Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@22e357dc"; line: 1, column: 4]
2026-01-28T17:54:29Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@49912c99"; line: 1, column: 4]
2026-01-28T17:54:29Z	note	Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@10163d6"; line: 1, column: 4]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

Table 13: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@1cbb87f3"; line: 1, column: 4]	1
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@22e357dc"; line: 1, column: 4]	1

reviewComment	count
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@49912c99"; line: 1, column: 4]	1
Unrecognized token 'org': was expecting (JSON String, Number, Array, Object or token 'null', 'true' or 'false') at [Source: (String)"org.eol.globi.domain.StudyImpl@10163d6"; line: 1, column: 4]	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

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⁵At time of writing (2026-01-28) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

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